

Impact of Group Investigation Strategy on Retention in Biology Concepts among Secondary School Students in Kwali Area Council, Abuja

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of Group Investigation Strategy on retention in Biology concepts among secondary school students in Kwali Area Council, Abuja. A quasi-experimental research design using a pre-test, post-test and delayed-post-test control group approach was adopted for the study. Two research questions and corresponding research hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consists of 2147 (Male, 13,268 & Female, 12,970) Government senior secondary school class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Kwali, Abuja. A sample size of 90 (Male, 47 & Female, 43) were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. The thirty (30) Biology Retention Test (BRT) items was developed by the researcher for data collection. It was validated and tested for reliability using Kuder Richardson formula 21 (K-R 21). A reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. The delayed posttest was conducted two weeks after the post-test; this was done in order to avoid retention error. The results showed that the use of Group Investigation Strategy enhances the retention ability of secondary school students than those exposed to conventional method. Hence, gender friendly. It was recommended that secondary schools, teachers should adopt the strategy (GIS) in teaching biology. Also, Professional bodies should organize seminars, workshops and conferences on the knowledge of Group Investigation Strategy for science teachers at federal and state levels.

Keyword: Group Investigation Strategy, Biology, Retention, Gender, Students' achievement

Introduction

Science education is a fundamental component of a nation's progress and development, serving as a catalyst for advancements in various fields. It is a critical component of education that is capable of reshaping an individual thought in particular and the society in general. The impact of Science education on national development is felt in several ways; as it provides humanity with knowledge about the environment, attitudes and values for social living, knowledge and skills to explore and transform resources, change in quality of life and improvement in economy (Katcha, 2010). Science education is therefore essential to the development of any nation that is why each nation must take it intense at all levels of learning (Abubakar & Olamoyegun, 2023).

Science has been regarded as the bedrock of modern-day technological breakthrough in that, it is the basis for all technological ideas seen in the world today (Babagana, Yaki & Abubakar, 2021). It is an organized body of knowledge that is self-directed towards solving human problems and also, providing solution to human needs. Science is viewed as the foundation of modern development and the connection among innovation technology and socio-economic development (Abubakar et al, 2021). The application of science has provided essential commodities such as drugs, clothing, fuel, food etc. In drugs, for example, we have antibiotics for infections, tranquilizers for nervous tensions, analgesic for pains etc. (Babagana, Yaki & Abubakar, 2021).

Science as school subjects comprises Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics, Agriculture and Biology. Biology is one of the core science subjects that senior secondary school students offer at the senior levels in Nigerian secondary schools. It is the science that connects us most intimately with nature by explaining well-being of man and other living organism around us. Biology knowledge enables humans understand their body, the environment in which they live and how other lives in the universe function (Apochi, Ebele & Abubakar, 2017). Due to advancement in biology, the world today has a healthier population. According to Adejoh and Apochi (2013), Biology occupies a central position in science; it is a life science which deals with living things, their existence and relationships with one another. Currently, Biology is offered in senior secondary schools by majority of the students. It is also a requirement for higher learning in a number of science-related professional courses like medicine, agriculture and pharmacy. Therefore, Biology is an important component of science programme because it provides students with a foundation of knowledge on the structure and function of living organisms (Abubakar, 2024). It teaches students the fundamentals of genetics, evolution, and ecology, as well as the basics of cellular and molecular biology.

The subject plays a crucial role in the social, economic, and technological development of a nation (Abubakar, Ogunseye & Ogunode, 2021).

Biology is very vast with many branches including zoology, genetics, ecology, botany, anatomy, physiology, histology, morphology, microbiology, molecular biology and the more advanced cell biology among others as illustrated below:

Source: Abubakar, (2018).
Fig. 1: Branches of Biology

Given the diverse branches of Biology and its applications across various human pursuits, its significance in economic development cannot be overstated. The enrollment of students in senior secondary school certificate examinations (SSCE) for Biology surpasses that for physics and chemistry, highlighting its widespread appeal (West African Examination Council, 2015). Despite its importance, observed trends in the performance of students in Biology at the senior secondary school level still leave room for improvement (Ahmed, 2014; Awobodu, 2016; Adebajo, 2019).

One potential factor that could contribute to the decline in students' performance in Biology exams is the utilization of ineffective teaching methods, particularly the conventional talk and chalk method. Teaching methods encompass the approaches used by educators to create a conducive learning environment, delineating the activities undertaken by both instructors and learners. These methods are broadly categorized into teacher-centered and student-centered approaches.

The teacher-centered approach often referred to as the conventional talk and chalk method, positions the teacher as the primary controller of the learning environment, limiting student engagement and participation. This method has been associated with poor retention of biology concepts among students in secondary schools. In contrast, the student-centered approach empowers learners to take an active role in their education, fostering independent, collaborative, cooperative, and competitive learning experiences.

One innovative student-centered approach that has shown promise in enhancing retention of biology concepts is the Group Investigation Strategy (GIS) (Ebele & Abubakar, 2019). GIS is a cooperative learning strategy where small groups of students collaborate to investigate a specific learning topic. This approach aims to develop students' beliefs, feelings, and attitudes towards the subject through democratic discussions, observations, and information sharing within the group. It encourages teamwork, self-reliance, and active participation among students.

In GIS, students are divided into groups to explore different aspects of a study issue, working collaboratively to investigate and interpret the topic. The information gathered is then compiled and presented to the entire class. This strategy promotes self-reliance, team-building, and the synthesis of diverse perspectives. The teacher's role is to guide students and make them aware of resources that may aid in their investigation.

GIS comprises four key components known as "The Four I's": investigation, interaction, interpretation, and intrinsic motivation (Tan, 2013). This approach has proven effective in fostering a deeper understanding of biology concepts among students and addresses the limitations associated with traditional teaching methods. It is illustrated in fig 2 below:

Source: (Sharan & Tan, 2013).

Figure 2: Components of Group Investigation Strategy

The advantages of using Group Investigation Strategy (GIS) extend to academic improvements across various curriculum domains, fostering positive interpersonal attitudes, good behaviors, values, and skills acquired through collaborative learning with GIS. Numerous researchers, including Johnson & Johnson (2000), Gillies (2004), and Sharan & Tan (2013), have proposed that GIS enhances student involvement, achievement, and retention in learning. Compared to conventional teaching methods, GIS is found to be more beneficial in developing basic cooperative skills, positive attitudes, values, improved group interaction and investigation, and verbal communication. It also encourages intrinsic motivation, a key component in sparking learners' interest in the GIS learning environment (Ebele & Abubakar, 2019).

GIS promotes investigation, interaction, elaboration, and listening by assigning critical roles to each group member, actively involving learners in the learning process and aiding in better understanding and retention of learned concepts. Working collaboratively in a group allows learners to assess their strengths and weaknesses, leveraging the group's diversity to achieve mutual goals.

Academically, Group Investigation and other collaborative learning strategies not only assist learners academically but also socially. Group learning can provide social benefits for students from diverse cultural backgrounds, enhancing social skills, self-competencies, self-esteem, and self-motivation, ultimately leading to more accurate results.

The effectiveness of Group Investigation Strategy in improving students' learning is attributed to several factors. It reduces competition, making the learning environment less intimidating for students and reducing reluctance to participate in investigations. It also fosters increased active participation and engagement in the classroom, diminishing the dominance of the teacher.

Retention, the ability to remember experiences and information learned at a later time, is influenced by various factors. Emotional experiences, age, and gender can impact retention. Emotional experiences, particularly painful ones, may be intentionally forgotten or repressed. Age plays a role, with retention generally increasing from infancy to the teenage years before decreasing in middle age and weakening further in old age. Farrant, as cited in Abubakar (2018), emphasized the importance of retention for knowledge acquisition, stating that the inability to retain what is learned hinders future performance.

Another variable to be considered here is gender. Gender is a social construct that differentiate male from female based on the physical features exhibited. Many researchers (Okoro, 2011; Abdu-Raheem, 2012 & Nnorom, 2015) have shown gender to be of significant influence in an investigation of this nature, hence the inclusion of gender as an intervening variable in the study.

Based on this background therefore, the present study intends to look at the impact of Group Investigation Strategy on retention in Biology concepts among secondary school students in Kwali Area Ccouncil, Abuja.

The concerning performance in Biology, as evidenced by several empirical studies (Ahmed, 2014; NECO & WAEC Chief Examiner's reports, 2015-2019), has garnered attention from stakeholders, including researchers. In Nigeria, the percentage of students passing biology in the senior school certificate examination at credit level and above (A1 – C6) consistently remained below required standard (WAEC, Chief Examiners' Report, 2019). Analysis indicates that in 2015, the percentage pass in the subject was 57.42%; 2016, 61.68%; 2017, 59.51%; 2018, 53.92%; 2019, 55.68% respectively.

Numerous factors have been identified as contributing to the declining trend in students' performance in Biology. Olatoye and Adekoya (2009) listed school-teacher related characteristics, teaching methods, social incentives, and others as potential influences. Researchers such as Yusuf and Afolabi (2010), Awobodu (2016), Raji (2017), and Adebajo (2019) linked poor performance and negative student attitudes toward biology to factors such as ineffective instructional strategies, poor teaching methods, the abstract nature of science concepts, the shortage of qualified biology teachers, inadequate infrastructure and laboratory facilities, teacher-centered instruction, and the lack of instructional materials.

Numerous studies, including those by Kareem (2003), Ahmed & Abimbola (2011), Umar (2011), and Orji & Ebele (2011), have identified poor teaching methods at the senior secondary school level in Nigeria as a major factor contributing to students' poor performance in biology. The issue is largely attributed to the use of ineffective teaching methods, particularly the conventional teacher-centered approach. Adebajo (2019) and Raji (2017) reported that a significant number of biology teachers in secondary schools rely on conventional methods, leading to consistently poor academic performance among students in biology. This emphasizes the urgency of addressing these factors, particularly ineffective teaching methods. The adoption of an innovative, student-centered strategy like GIS has the potential to improve overall performance in sciences, specifically biology.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of the study is to investigate the impact of Group Investigation Strategy on retention in Biology concepts among secondary school students in Kwali Area Council, Abuja. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. Find out the retention ability between students who are exposed to Group Investigation Strategy and those exposed to conventional method.
2. Determine whether gender has any effect on students' retention ability when exposed to Group Investigation Strategy.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. What is the mean retention ability score between students taught Biology using group Investigation Strategy and those exposed to conventional method?
2. What is the mean retention ability score between male and female students taught Biology using group Investigation Strategy?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

1. **HO₁:** There is no significant difference between the mean retention ability score of students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy and those exposed to conventional method
2. **HO₂:** There is no significant difference between the mean retention ability score of male and female students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy.

Methodology

The study employed a quasi-experimental design with a pre-test, post-test, and delayed-post-test control group approach. The pre-test aimed to assess students' prior knowledge of biology concepts before teaching, while the post-test gauged their understanding after exposure to the treatment. The experimental group received instruction using the Group Investigation Strategy (GIS), while the control group was taught through conventional methods. Intact classes were utilized to maintain normal class settings and school timetable.

The population of the study consisted of 2,147 (Male, 13,268 & Female, 12,970) Government senior secondary school class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Kwali, Abuja. A sample size of 90 (Male, 47 & Female, 43) SSII Biology students were selected from the target population using simple random technique. Thirty (30) Biology Retention Test (BRT) items was developed by the researcher for data collection based on the following topics: digestive system, transport system, respiratory system, excretory system, nutrient cycling, and decomposition in nature, ecological management and pollution. The BRT was validated and tested for reliability using Kuder Richardson formula 21 (K-R 21). A reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. The delayed posttest was conducted two weeks after the post-test; this was done in order to avoid retention error.

Data analysis employed percentage, frequency count, means, and standard deviation to answer research questions. Hypotheses were tested using the t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The data obtained from the study were presented using mean, standard deviation to answer research question and t-test statistical analysis to test hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question 1:

What is the mean retention ability score between students taught Biology using group Investigation Strategy and those exposed to conventional method?

To answer this research question, frequency count, mean and standard deviation were used and the results set out on Table 2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on Retention of Students Exposed to Group Investigation Strategy and the Conventional Groups.

Groups	No. of Students	Mean Scores		Standard Deviation	Mean Gain
		Pre-test	Retention		

Group Investigation Strategy	46	14.20	26.18	10.55	11.98
Conventional Method	44	13.96	14.04	11.44	0.08
Mean Difference		0.24	12.14		11.90
Total	90				

Source: (Field Survey, 2023)

Table 2 indicates the means and standard deviation on the pre-test and retention of students exposed to both the Group Investigation Strategy and Conventional method. From the table, the mean gain in retention of the students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy was 11.98 while the others who were taught using Conventional method was 0.08. The overall mean difference between the groups was 11.90 in favour of students who were taught using Group Investigation Strategy. It therefore means that the mean retention score of students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy was higher than those taught using Conventional Method with a mean gain difference of 11.90 which favoured the experimental group.

Research Question 2:

What is the mean retention ability score between male and female students taught Biology using group Investigation Strategy? To answer this research question, frequency count, mean and standard deviation were used and the results set out on Table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on Retention of Male and Female Students Exposed to Group Investigation Strategy

Gender	No. of Students	Mean Scores		Standard Deviation	Mean Gain
		Pre-test	Retention		
Male	26	14.50	25.14	10.50	10.64
Female	20	13.94	24.98	11.42	11.04
Mean Difference		0.56	0.16		0.40
Total	46				

Source: (Field Survey, 2023)

Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation on retention of male and female students who were taught Biology. From the table, the mean gain in retention of the male students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy was 10.64 while those of the female students was 11.04. It therefore showed that the overall mean difference between the groups was 0.40. The implication is that the mean retention score of male and female students who were taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy had an overall difference in mean gain of 0.40.

Hypotheses

HO₁:

There is no significant difference between the mean retention ability score of students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy and those exposed to conventional method.

To test for this hypothesis, t-test statistic was used and the results presented in Table 4.

Table 4: t-test Result in respect of Mean Retention Scores between the Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	N	\bar{X}	SD	t – value	df	P	Decision
Experimental	46	26.18	10.55	7.39	88	0.000	Significant
Control	44	14.05	11.44				

Source: (Field Survey, 2023)

P>0.05 Significant

Result in Table 4, showed that, the calculated t-test value was 7.39, df was 88 and the p-value was 0.000. This indicates it is significant. Based on the analysis, the hypothesis was rejected. In other words, respondents from both groups differed significantly in their mean retention scores which favoured the experimental group who were taught using the Group Investigation Strategy.

HO₂:

There is no significant difference between the mean retention ability score of male and female students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy.

To test for this hypothesis, t-test statistic was used and the results presented in Table 5.

Table 5: t-test Result in respect of Mean Retention Scores between the Male and Female Students Exposed to Group Investigation Strategy

Groups	N	\bar{X}	SD	t – value	df	P	Decision
Male	26	26.14	10.50	0.11	44	0.622	Not Significant
Female	20	25.91	11.42				

Source: (Field Survey, 2023)

Result in Table 5, showed that, the calculated t-test value was 0.11, df was 44 and the p- value was 0.622. This indicates it is not significant. Based on the analysis, the hypothesis was retained in other words; students from both groups did not differ significantly in their mean retention scores.

Discussion of Findings

The data presented in Table 2 provide answer to question one. Finding shows that, the mean retention score of students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy was higher than those taught using Conventional Method which favoured the experimental group.

The result of t-test as reported in Table 4 showed that, it is significant. Based on the analysis, the hypothesis was rejected. In other words, respondents from both groups differed significantly in their mean retention scores which favoured the experimental group who were taught using the Group Investigation Strategy. The findings of the current work are in line with 'Nireti and Olubumi (2014) who found that there were significant main effects of treatment on students' achievement as well as retention in experimental group. Farrant (2002) believed that increase in knowledge lies solely on the ability to remember. He further explained that if an individual could not grasp and keep hold of what was taught and learnt, it would seem like trying to fill a bucket without bottom with water. This means that if one cannot retain what one learnt then there is no need expecting one to perform in that activity in the future. To further support this idea, Chianson (2008) stated that retention in biology is not acquired by mere rote learning but through appropriate instructional delivery approach. Similarly, Katcha, Orji, Ebele, Abubakar & Babagana (2018) found a significant difference between experimental and control groups. On the contrary, Ndukwe (2000) found no significant difference when the two groups (expository versus project-centered methods) were compared on the retention test.

The reason could be based on the fact that retention in biology is not acquired by mere rote learning but through appropriate instructional delivery approach like GIS which helped to facilitate and encourage retention of biology concepts leading to significant difference.

The data presented in Table 3 provide answer to question two. Finding shows that, the mean retention score of male and female students who were taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy did not differ much.

The result of t-test as reported in Table 5 showed that, it is not significant. Based on the analysis, the hypothesis was retained in other words; students from both groups did not differ significantly in their mean retention scores. The findings of this research agrees with that of Oludipe (2012), who found no significant difference in academic achievement of male and female students at the pre-test, post-test and delayed post-test (retention) levels respectively in basic science. Similarly, Yaki, Babagana, & Abubakar, (2020) found that, there are no significant differences between male and female students in Biology. However, the

male students achieved better than female students in science concepts. Also, the findings of this research is in line with that of Orji, Apochi & Abubakar, 2018) who found that, there are no significant differences between male and female students.

The reason could be based on the fact that GIS motivated and facilitated the retention ability of male and female students equally leading to non-significant difference.

Conclusion

The researchers however, concluded based on the analysis of the results in this study, that the use of Group Investigation Strategy enhances the retention ability of secondary school students than the conventional method. With GIS, students learnt better about Biology, carried out their responsibilities and made effort to achieve a stated objective. It can be deduced that GIS enhanced cooperation and interaction, curiosity and increases retention of learnt concept than conventional method. It was also demonstrated that GIS do not discriminate on the basis of sexes and hence the retention of male and female students exposed to it did not differ significantly in their mean retention scores which attest to its gender-friendly nature.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in this study the following recommendations were made:

1. Since the use of Group Investigation Strategy has been established to improve student's retention of Biology concepts in secondary schools, teachers should be encouraged to adopt GIS in teaching biology.
2. Professional bodies like Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) in collaboration with the Nigeria Educational Research and Development Centre (NERDC), Federal Ministry of Education and school proprietors should organize seminars, workshops and conferences on the knowledge of Group Investigation Strategy for science teachers at federal and state levels. If this training is done on regular basis the science teachers will be proficient in the use of innovative strategy like Group Investigation Strategy in teaching biology.

Acknowledgements

I want to acknowledge Prof. Hauwa Imam (Director, Institute of Education) for her tremendous effort and support towards the success of this study. I say thank you. I appreciate the contributions of Prof. M.A. Katcha, Dr. R.G.Dajal, Dr. M.A. Apochi and Prof. U.S. Anaduaka (Director Quality Assurance) my colleagues in the Department of Science and Environmental Education, Faculty of Education, University of Abuja for their moral support; and all who have contributed in no small measure to put this work together.

Finally, the principals, Biology teachers and other staff of the sample schools also deserve appreciation. I also thank the SS2 Biology students from the two sample schools who took part in the study. I am indeed grateful for their tremendous assistance, understanding, cooperation and support towards the success of this study.

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